

HRD Climate in Pharmaceutical Industries

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Abstract

The main aim of present research was to examine the temperament of HRD-climate in pharmaceutical companies and identify the factors conducive towards HRD-climate. HRD climate plays a very important role in the success of any organization because directly or indirectly it affects the performance of the employees. If the HRD climate is good then the employees will contribute their maximum for the achievement of the organizational objectives. The current research is an attempt to identify the HRD-climate in pharmaceutical companies in Indore city. For this study the researcher used descriptive research design. The universe of the study constituted of 150 different categories employees from two pharmaceutical companies. Among them 75 employees were selected by using purposive sampling. The researcher used questionnaire method to collect the data from the primary source.

Keywords:- HRD-climate, Executive, Non- Executive, pharmaceutical Industries.

Introduction: -

An organisation, in this manner, relies upon individuals for their endurance and development. Along these lines, individuals need organisations. By far most of individuals work to help themselves and their families. Be that as it may, individuals work for some reasons other than financial security. For instance they may likewise work to keep occupied and feel valuable, to make and accomplish something. They need to pick up acknowledgment and accomplish status or to test and stretch their capacities. HRM is worried about the powerful utilization of individuals to accomplish authoritative and singular objectives. It is a method for overseeing individuals at work, with the goal that they give their best to the organisation. It might be characterized as the craft of obtaining, creating and keeping up a skilled workforce to accomplish the objectives of an organisation in a successful and effective way. Human Resource Development is a positive idea in Human Resource Management. It depends on the conviction that an interest in Human Beings is essential and will constantly acquire significant advantages to the association over the long haul. It goes for by and large advancement of HR so as to add to the prosperity of the workers, association and the general public on the loose.

HRD: A Humanistic Concept

- People can do better; they can do wonders.
- Involve them, trust them and empower them: treat them as resource, as assets.

- Focus on the strengths of the People and help them overcome their weaknesses.
- Integrate the needs and aspirations of Individuals into the strategic goals and the mission of an organisation – for better results.
- Encourage individual initiative and response by providing a fostering culture (Openness, trust, collaboration, mutuality etc.)

According to Prof. T.V. Rao, “HRD is a process by which the employees of an organisation are helped in a continuous and planned way to put it plainly, HRD targets helping individuals to procure capabilities required to play out the entirety of their capacities viably and cause their association to progress nicely.”

HRD Climate includes Three (3) Components

1) General Climate (GC)

2) OCTAPAC

(Openness, Confrontation, Trust, Autonomy, Pro Action, Collaboration)

3) HRD Mechanism

To start with the general atmosphere things, center around the significance given to HR advancement by the top administration and line chiefs, all in all. The OCTAPAC things manage the degree to which Openness, Confrontation, Trust, Autonomy, Proactivity, Authenticity, Collaboration are esteemed and advanced in the association.

Essential factors of HRD mechanisms Performance Appraisal helps primarily in enabling an individual to develop his present role capabilities. Potential Appraisal helps in identifying the employees' future likely role

with an organization. Training aims at developing individual employee's personal effectiveness and develops his ability to perform his job (present or future), strengthens interpersonal relationship and increase team work and collaboration. Feedback and performance appraisal helps in the development of individual as well as supervisor and subordinate relationships. Organizational development means a mechanism of developing team collaboration and self-renewing skills and capabilities.

Review Of Literature: -

Deepak Kumar Gupta, Subhankar Das Et. al. (2019) directed research on "HRD atmosphere in chose open division banks in India" and found in their exploration that It is uncovered from the present investigation that the general atmosphere of SBI is better with contrast with UCO bank. Along these lines, the top administration of UCO bank must be increasingly concerned and cautious for the improvement of their officials. As respects OCTAPACE culture both of the banks observed to be at a similar level while the HRD instrument framework is superior to that of UCO bank. So HRD sub-stems should be increasingly straightforward for the officials of the UCO bank towards by and large authoritative improvement.

Dr. Rashmi Bhatia, Dr. Arun Bhatia (2019) led inquire about on "A Comparative Study on Models of Organizational Culture in Higher Education in India" and found in their examination Each and every model talked about above has its very own unmistakable highlights. For instance, Denison (1995) takes a more extensive view and covers different authoritative perspectives, while Pareek (2002) stresses on qualities and procedure. Then again, Hofstede's accentuation is on culturally diverse measurements (2010). For instructive organization's social examination, Cameron's (2011) model is progressively proper as it identifies with the way of life of the instructive establishment.

Dhall and Sinha (2018) led examine on "Interceding impact of TQM on connection between hierarchical culture and execution: proof from Indian SMEs" and found in the exploration that The consequences of this examination have recognized some significant regions for future research. Future examinations might be done in different enterprises, locales and countries to

further look at if the reasonable model fits into their tasks, which would give further approval of the model proposed in this investigation.

Geetanjali, Bhambhani et. al. (2018) directed research on "An Empirical Research on Impact of HRD Climate on Infosys Pune" and found in their exploration that The examination was started to check effect of HRD-atmosphere in Infosys. The consequence of the examination includes 50 respondents from Infosys. The connection investigation it has been seen that every one of the three segments HRD Mechanisms, General atmosphere and OCTAPACE Culture are exceptionally related to one another the estimation of r is going untruths 0.687 to 0.834, which obviously expressed that variety in single segment will have solid impact on other two segments. Single direction anova uncovers that age conjugal status and experience has no effect on HRD-atmosphere of Infosys. Likewise, Friedmen test uncovers HRD instruments is profoundly affecting component of HRD atmosphere with mean position of 2.14.

Suvarna Lapalekar, Kamlesh Bhandari (2017) led look into on "OCTAPACE Culture: A Predictor of workforce execution" and found in their exploration that the eight factors of HRD atmosphere in this way plays a crucial and basic job in upkeep and improvement of representatives, which would prompt higher fulfilment in their activity. OCTAPACE in type of Human asset advancement is a ceaseless procedure to guarantee the improvement of worker's skills, dynamism, inspiration and viability in a methodical and arranged way. In this investigation all out 500 workforce were chosen and through survey they were gotten some information about the way of life exist in their associations. For the examination, connection and relapse were connected. The discoveries uncover that there is a critical effect of OCTAPACE culture on workforce execution.

Objectives Of The Study:-

1. To study the HRD Climate prevailing in selected MSMEs in Bhavnagar District.
2. To study the differences in the perception of employees based on designation.

Hypotheses Of The Study:-

H01: Employees don't Get Freedom and Have less Importance in Organization.

H02: Employees don't get freedom and are afraid to express or discuss their feelings and ideas with their superior and subordinates.

H03: Seniors don't help juniors to identify their strength & weaknesses and don't help them to solve the mistakes no Punishment for mistakes.

H04: Employees doesn't trust each other in organization.

H05: Top management doesn't delegate the authority to motivate juniors to handle higher responsibilities.

H06: Employees are not sponsored for training & development program by the organization.

H07: Organization doesn't have their special mechanisms to reward employees and take special care to appreciate it.

H08: Organization's performance appraisal system is not based on objective assessment.

H09: Career Opportunities are not pointed out to juniors by senior officers.

H010: Job rotation in the organization doesn't facilitate employee's development.

Methodology:-

Population of the Study is Employees working in Pharmaceutical Industries. Primary data collected through Structured Questionnaire. Coding of variables in quantitative research is very critical for better interpretation of results. Age, total experience, designation, team size, total duration and total value of the project were

Analysis And Interpretation:-

all coded and were entered in to the computer. The questions and responses were coded and entered in the computer using Microsoft Excel software. A five-point likert scale was designed to gauge the responses in part B. The scales ranged from strongly agree (5) to strongly disagree (1).

Sample And Sample Size:-

The primary data collected from 75 employees of two Pharmaceutical Industries in Indore city were selected for the study that comes around were coded, classified and analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 22.0).The tools used for analysis of primary data were cross-tabulation, descriptive statistics like arithmetic mean, standard deviation, variance, frequency etc., the tools used for hypothesis testing t-test.

Statistical Tool:-

In order to efficiently use the survey method a questionnaire was developed. The questionnaire was intricately designed. The data collection tool is divided into two parts. Part A covers the information related to respondents like name, designation, and organisation, category of organisation, email id, gender, cadre, education qualification, age group and awareness regarding HRD Climate. This will help the researcher to identify various information and one can analyse the same based on different parameters.

Table No.: 01
T – Test Analysis – General Climates

General Climate	Employee Cadre	N	Mean	S.D.	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Employees Get Freedom and Have Enough Importance in Organization	Executive	30	2.45	1.34	0.2446	0.6116	0.5427
	Non - Executive	45	2.62	1.06	0.1580		

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare Overall HRD Climate in Executive and Non- Executive cadre of employees working in Pharmaceutical Industries. There was no significant

difference in the scores for Executive and Non- Executive conditions ($p > 0.05$). These results suggest that General Climate is really having positive effect on employees except few parameters needs some refinement.

Table No.:02
T – Test Analysis – OCTAPAC

OCTAPAC	Employee Cadre	N	Mean	S.D.	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Employees should get freedom and are not afraid to express or discuss their feelings and ideas with their superior and subordinates.	Executive	30	1.66	1.08	0.1972	4.3066	0.0001
	Non - Executive	45	2.72	1.02	0.1521		

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare Overall HRD Climate in Executive and Non- Executive cadre of employees working in Pharmaceutical Industries. There was no

significant difference in the scores for Executive and Non- Executive conditions ($p < 0.05$). These results suggest that OCTAPAC is really having positive effect on employees except few parameters needs some refinement.

Table No.:03
T – Test Analysis – OCTAPAC

OCTAPAC	Employee Cadre	N	Mean	S.D.	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Seniors help juniors to identify their strength & weaknesses and help them to solve the mistakes if any made by juniors in place of punishing them.	Executive	30	2.32	1.44	0.2629	2.8173	0.0062
	Non - Executive	45	3.18	1.19	0.1774		

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare Overall HRD Climate in Executive and Non- Executive cadre of employees working in Pharmaceutical Industries. There was no significant

difference in the scores for Executive and Non-Executive conditions ($p < 0.05$). These results suggest that OCTAPAC is really having positive effect on employees except few parameters needs some refinement.

Table No.: 04
T – Test Analysis – OCTAPAC

OCTAPAC	Employee Cadre	N	Mean	S.D.	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Employees trust each other in organization.	Executive	30	2.05	1.96	0.3578	3.0228	0.0035
	Non - Executive	45	3.12	1.10	0.1640		

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare Overall HRD Climate in Executive and Non- Executive cadre of

employees working in Pharmaceutical Industries. There was no significant difference in the scores for Executive and Non-Executive conditions ($p <$

0.05). These results suggest that OCTAPAC except few parameters needs some refinement. is really having positive effect on employees

Table No.: 05, T – Test Analysis – OCTAPAC

OCTAPAC	Employee Cadre	N	Mean	S.D.	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Delegation of authority to motivate juniors to handle higher responsibilities and juniors will take it as an opportunity for their development.	Executive	30	2.88	1.31	0.2392	2.5994	0.0113
	Non - Executive	45	1.91	1.74	0.2594		

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare Overall HRD Climate in Executive and Non- Executive cadre of employees working in Pharmaceutical Industries. There was no significant

difference in the scores for Executive and Non-Executive conditions ($p < 0.05$). These results suggest that OCTAPAC is really having positive effect on employees except few parameters needs some refinement.

Table No.: 06, T – Test Analysis – OCTAPAC

OCTAPAC	Employee Cadre	N	Mean	S.D.	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Employees are sponsored for training & development program by the organization based on genuine needs of training employees take a seriously for individual & organizational development.	Executive	30	2.77	1.09	0.1990	4.6287	0.0001
	Non - Executive	45	1.36	1.41	0.2102		

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare Overall HRD Climate in Executive and Non- Executive cadre of employees working in Pharmaceutical Industries. There was significant difference in the scores for Executive and Non-

Executive conditions ($p < 0.05$). These results suggest that this parameter of OCTAPAC is really having Negative effect on employees. It may create disputes between Executive and Non- Executive Cadre of Employees. So, this parameters needs some refinement.

Table No.: 07

T – Test Analysis – HRD Mechanism

HRD Mechanism	Employee Cadre	N	Mean	S.D.	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Organization has their special mechanisms to reward employees and take special care to appreciate it.	Executive	30	2.44	1.21	0.2209	0.7764	0.4400
	Non - Executive	45	2.19	1.46	0.2176		

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare Overall HRD Climate in Executive and Non- Executive cadre of employees working in Pharmaceutical Industries. There was no significant difference in the scores for Executive and

Non-Executive conditions ($p > 0.05$). These results suggest that HRD Mechanism is really having positive effect on employees except few parameters needs some refinement.

Table No.: 08
T – Test Analysis – HRD Mechanism

HRD Mechanism	Employee Cadre	N	Mean	S.D.	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Organization's performance appraisal system is based on objective assessment and any weakness found will be communicated to the employees in positive way in place of threatening way.	Executive	30	1.81	1.33	0.2428	3.3019	0.0015
	Non - Executive	45	2.75	1.12	0.1670		

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare Overall HRD Climate in Executive and Non- Executive cadre of employees working in Pharmaceutical Industries. There was no significant difference in the scores for Executive and

Non- Executive conditions ($p < 0.05$). These results suggest that HRD Mechanism is really having positive effect on employees except few parameters needs some refinement.

Table No.: 09
T – Test Analysis – HRD Mechanism

HRD Mechanism	Employee Cadre	N	Mean	S.D.	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Career Opportunities are pointed out to juniors by senior officers.	Executive	30	1.65	1.19	0.2173	0.8993	0.3715
	Non - Executive	45	1.42	1.01	0.1506		

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare Overall HRD Climate in Executive and Non- Executive cadre of employees working in Pharmaceutical Industries. There was no significant difference in the scores for Executive and

Non- Executive conditions ($p > 0.05$). These results suggest that HRD Mechanism is really having positive effect on employees except few parameters needs some refinement.

Table No.: 10
T – Test Analysis – HRD Mechanism

HRD Mechanism	Employee Cadre	N	Mean	S.D.	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Job rotation in the organization facilitates employee's development.	Executive	30	2.37	1.51	0.2757	1.0362	0.3035
	Non - Executive	45	2.02	1.38	0.2057		

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare Overall HRD Climate in Executive and Non- Executive cadre of employees working in Pharmaceutical Industries. There was no significant difference in the scores for Executive and

Non-Executive conditions ($p > 0.05$). These results suggest that HRD Mechanism is really having positive effect on employees except few parameters needs some refinement.

Findings:-

1. More than respondents believed that they are getting enough freedom and importance in their concern organization.
2. More than respondents believed that their concern organisations' policies facilitate employees' development.
3. More than respondents believed that their concern organisations' top management putting efforts to identify and utilize their potentials.
4. More than believed that they are getting enough freedom to express their feelings and ideas with their superiors and subordinates.
5. More than respondents believed that when problems arise people are discussing these problems openly and will try to solve them rather accusing each other behind the back.
6. More than respondents believed that their seniors are helping them to identify their strength and weakness and are also helping them to solve the mistakes if they made.
7. Less than respondents believed that they trust each other in their respective organisation. This is believed by them from their past experience with their colleague.
8. Less than respondents believed that they are not getting motivation form their top management to implement innovative and creative ideas for organisational development.
9. More than respondents believed that Top Management delegate the authority to motivate juniors to handle higher responsibilities.
10. Less than respondents believed that their respective organisations' top management identifying their potentials and competencies.
11. More than respondents believed that they are getting sponsorship from their respective organisations for training and development programs, which they should be provided for individual as well as organisational development point of view.
12. More than respondents believed that they are able to apply the concept called T.E.A.M. (Together Everyone Achieves More) and they get support of each other's strengths & weaknesses.
13. More than respondents believed that Promotion discuss are based on the contemporary and abilities rather than based on any favouritism. It will damage their working performance individually as well as organisational performances.
14. More than respondents believed that their respective organisations has special

mechanisms to reward them for their performances and their respective organisations also taking special steps to appreciate their best performances. It will motivate to this category of employees.

15. More than respondents believed that their concern Organization's performance appraisal system is based on objective assessment.

16. More than respondents believed that senior officers from their concern organisations are pointing out in identifying career opportunities available for them.

17. More than respondents believed that in their respective organisations, Job rotation facilitates employee's development.

18. Less than respondents believed that seniors don't guide their juniors and prepare them for their future responsibilities / roles they are likely to take up in the future.

Limitations Of The Study:-

1. The organizational culture and climate of Pharmaceutical Industries which are located in Indore city were only considered.

2. The research study was focused only of HRD Climate.

3. This research study was carried out in Pharmaceutical Industries of private sector; the findings of the study may not applicable to other types of organization.

4. The data is based on individual opinion, which may bring in some bias or it may change with time.

Conclusion:

1. General Climate and HRD Mechanism are under Questionable level of Internal Consistency in Cronbach's Alpha reliability test as both are less than 0.7. Promotions are still based on favouritism observed in many organizations, which indicates urgent need to improve promotion policy. Employees must provide the motivation to utilise and implement best of their innovative and creative ideas in their concern organisation. Employees must be given freedom to express their ideas and feelings with their staff.

Employees must be given guidance and suggestions regarding their mistakes in place of punishments. The study reveals that employees expecting support for training programs from 2.Top management, as these training programs will be useful for the development of both Individuals as well as organizations. Employees from each cadre must be provided counselling and mentoring

to develop and maintain the TEAM (Together Everyone Achieves More) concept.

3. Top management needs to set up competency mapping mechanism in their concern organization. Pharmaceutical Industries in Indore city must adopt Performance appraisal and

Promotion system which should be biased free and objective. Pharmaceutical Industries should create best working environment where, each one feeling sense of full trust on each other. Overall, OCTAPAC is fabulous which is truly good sign for the development of

employees as well as their organisations.

4. In this research study, research found that in comparing to large scale organisations people trust more on each other and working together for their own as well as organisational development point of view. It has also found by the researcher that even though promotions on front taking place based on objectivity but still some of the old fashioned organisations promoting their employees based on YES BOSS approach, which can harm those organisations in long run. This research study also reveals that almost 45% of the respondents' replied can't say when it comes to asking about team work in the organisation. It's amazing to know that even though seniors truly guide their juniors for certain development related activities.

5. It has also observed by the research in this research study based on their cadre even though most of the respondents were belongs to Non- Executive category and Executive category, but the good part of this is most from non- executives also knowing about this concepts and working positively in their respective organisations.

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